

on crucial issues of public concern through articles in print media, public lectures, and professional academic works over the years. In that, those reflections have not been purely by-products of my that professional engagement as a member of the academia: in a critical sense, those have been intimately informed by my encounters with the world beyond my professional domain such as my association with social activists, not only from the state and the region but also, from the rest of the country, and those interactions I have had with many key actors in the socio-political and economic life of the state, particularly during the last decade. This aspect of my intellectual and political life, I suspect, is a natural outcome of the general orientation which has been shaped by the peculiarities of my existential locations (e.g., as a member of a particular place or culture or profession), something that hints at me, as fellow academics called it "subject position".

A critical part of my existential location has been the experience associated with the absence of Manipur (or India's Northeast in general) in the academic literature as well as in the ("national") media. This invisibility or absence has been a crucial driving force behind my enquiries on identity politics and the ideas associated with "nation- state". Consequently, over the years, this absence has come to reveal critical presence of ideas and practices which have hitherto been obscured or camouflaged behind the ideas of "India" and "Manipur". and other "nationalist" articulations such as that of the "Naga nationalists".

Another aspect of this absence has also been, especially as someone who has been staying outside one's "home state", the sense of being dislocated or being cut off from one's own moorings on a daily basis. On the other hand, the same process also produces the sense of being out of place or not being at home in the "national" collective as the (national) media, the "print capital" that fosters "imagined community", renders Manipur and India's Northeast in general invisible. But today, thanks to the advent of internet, some

parts of that experience have changed, the general invisibility of events in Manipur in the "national" media has no longer deprived me of following the daily happenings in the state. There are web sites of the dailies published in Manipur and the region as well as other dedicated portals. While the so-called "mainstream" may continue to be by and large disconnected with its own proclaimed selfhood even in an increasingly connected world, people like me do feel much more connected with one's "home" while still being away physically from the same today.

Thus, these new developments have provided one to connect and engage with the events in Manipur and the region in general. Moreover, during the last decade, besides reading news or opinions of various commentators and observers on the local media, every visit to Manipur has been a privileged moment to learn and experience firsthand the life and times in my home state. Indeed, my encounters with the lived and quotidian world of the ordinary life in Manipur, marked by informal conversations with people from various walks of life, their snide remarks, offhand jokes and anecdotes, which they shared with me sometimes with laughter and often with cynicism or sighs of helplessness and resignation, have been windows to the various shades of their native experiences with the tumultuous and increasingly murky life in the state. Besides such quotidian worlds, I have also experienced the stage of high culture and politics; from those academic seminars that I have been a part of to those public meetings and commemorations which I have witnessed on TV or attended as a speaker or as a member of the public, sitting amidst my fellow citizens, watching and listening to those who spoke on and for the people of the state - all have been invaluable experiences. Even those moments wherein I was exposed to the aspects of the oppressive and violent environment have been instructive, albeit those experiences are not something that I like to encounter in life.

And not to forget, my interactions with Manipuri diasporas, particularly the professionals and students in Delhi and those cities I have visited, have given me insights about who and what we are as a people. Over the years, these interactions have revealed the ingenuity as well as the dogged nature of our cultural traits, including

those negative traits which, one expects, should have neutralized through the different cultural exposures. In some sense, the groups of diasporas are the microcosmic representations of the society back home with all its ills and shortcomings and strengths. However, I have also seen the potential of the community of diasporas that do provide a glimmer of hope for a resurgence to reverse the systemic failures --- the normative and institutional decadence in Manipur

INDIVIDUAL AND DECADENT SOCIETY: REFLECTIONS ON POLITICAL CULTURE

The intention behind starting this write up with a note on personal experience and its relationship with knowledge is not merely to state the premise of a knowledge. It is an exercise to remind oneself, and also the readers, the importance of a conversation between life and letter on the one hand, and on the other, the linkages between epistemic issues and political or ideological moorings. And there is a need to be aware of one's "subject position, which, in turn, foregrounds individuality and its capacity to engage in informed and reasoned deliberations.

I am more than aware that this assertion on the importance of individuality will come to many in Manipur as a politically incorrect or undesirable assertion. Such a reservation could be a product of equating the individuality capable of informed and reasoned deliberation with alienated individual, the one who has failed to be in touch with oneself (or inner world) in her or his umbilical relation to fellow beings and larger society. It is also quite likely that such reservation is also a manifestation of the pathos of our society.¹

Indeed, the subversion normative aspects of life and the collapsing or defunct institutional mechanisms in Manipur indicate that people have more or less shrunk into the domain of their individual private interests in the state. Sustaining such a scenario has been the unholy marriage, between feudal ethos of the past and remnants of external paramount power, which has produced a political culture that re-produces and reinforces status based forms of social dealings. The decadence that we see is a pointer to the presence of alienated individuals in our society. In fact, the decadence of the unholy marriage has sustained a society with a deeply entrenched status-based ethos

while simultaneously subverting, amongst others, individuality and individual's capacity to have informed and reasoned dialogues. In fact, it is quite possible that an overt display of preference for an expression "we" over "I" is a defense for the guilt of the alienated individual (egos). After all, Manipur is replete with stories and reality of the mushrooming groups and factions, the plethora of such groups and factions are not necessarily the results of ideological or programmatic differences. The unattended decades old violent armed conflict(s) has only aggravated the subversion of a culture of dialogue and reasoned deliberations.

The political culture has also nurtured one's capacity to induce sycophancy amongst the people as the sole yardstick to measure the success of leadership. Simultaneously, it has also encouraged a re-enactment of rituals and ethos that smack of feudal and imperial order, and correspondingly sheer dishonesty and hypocrisy are allowed to often pass off as standards of decency and modesty. Thus, the public posture of "*Meeyam bu eekok non-duna khurumjari...meeyamnashu hen-na khangbiramganee...adubu.. karishu khangjadraba tol-laba eige waaknalna phaojabada haijaraga...*" to the private conviction of "*gyan taada-ba, kok yaodaba meeyaam se..*" "*maana kari khongdana...karishu khang-dabane makhoido*" continue to complement the split selves who inhabit a fragmented society.

The above political culture also reaffirms the marginalized nature of Manipur vis-à-vis the Indian State. And like most marginalized people, people in Manipur often act like "crabs in the bucket", pulling each other down or indulging in cynical criticism (as it is called in Manipuri *sidhaba*). In fact, true to the spirit of the status based social dealings and "crabs in the bucket" mentality which seems to have become crucial aspects of their national characteristic. one often gets to hear personalized remarks even while discussing issues of public or intellectual concerns. Thus, a typical refrain like "the problem with *her/him*" rather than "the problem with *what she/he says* or *her/his views*" would often surface as a way of expressing disagreement or observation in casual conversations or serious deliberations.²

With such cultural traits, one tends to be overwhelmed by the cacophony of assertions of the powerful that insist that "right to education is more important than the right to life" or "reading book won't do" of those who dismissed intellectual inputs and harped on "actions" as if "actions" do not have ideational and ethical components. Incidentally, the cacophony also have voices from even professional academicians who wittingly or unwittingly subvert themselves by devaluing the importance of theoretical insights by harping on what they called "ground reality" as if professionals who are associated with social sciences do not engage in activities called "empirical research" or "grounded theories" or social researches that rest on political commitment or premise (such as followed by feminist researchers).

Amidst the fragmentations and divisive tendencies — as a senior journalist from Manipur once puts it to me in his inimitable style: "Two Meiteis, three organizations", a phenomenon different from those divisions based on "tribal" or religious loyalty, the overt preference for the expression of "we" over "I" increasingly appears to be nothing but what psychoanalysts call, "defence mechanism" against the lurking and powerful individual egos that characterize the ensuing alienation.

Given such normalizing and normalized realities of the murky socio-political world of contemporary Manipur wherein resistant and resisted, protector and predator or victim and victimizer become increasingly indistinguishable, and normative aspects of life and crucial institutional mechanisms have been often subverted in the name of "practical" and "strategic" actions/choices in the service of justifications for the acts that foster those subversions and decadence, it seems pertinent that one must find one's own inner conviction and its dynamics. After all, it is arguably the last vanguard of human agency and in the given state of affairs in Manipur, it is "ultimately". as a gentleman who has seen Manipur much more and longer than I do puts it, "the source of change" for the larger collectivity.

However, the inner conviction of the individual can only truly be arrived at through a process of self-reflection by which one seeks

to be in touch with one's "inner" world in its umbilical relation to the "outside" world. And to be of any consequence for the collective, such conviction must also confront the public domain and be subjected to its scrutiny. Only then its evolutionary trajectory as well as its shortcomings and strengths can be meaningfully engaged or understood.

Over the last decade, much of my interventions in the form of writings, lectures, public speeches and deliberations (both private and public) have been efforts to remind these debilitating aspects that afflict our mind and actions. In its essence, this essay is a re-visit to some of those issues.

As I see it, this re-visit has become particularly crucial for two reasons. First, many of those issues continue to haunt the state till date. Second, aspects of the dominant perspectives and terms of discourses on critical issues of the state, which I have tried to confront in those writings, have more or less continued to hold their sway amongst significant socio-political actors in the state. However, I shall restrict myself to those issues associated with the question of identity under the rubric of "Political Culture, Identity Politics, and Destiny of Manipur", For, this issue has critically affected the socio- political and economic life of the people in the state in the last few decades. The recurrent economic blockade, the unsavory incidents such as the one at Mao that led to the death of two young lives following what seemed to have come to many as an unexpected plan of Mr. Th. Muivah, General Secretary of NSCN (I-M), to visit Manipur, and demand for "Alternative Arrangement" etc have renewed people's attention to the "politics of recognition", something that has to do with the issues of identity.

Since I have indicated that this exercise shall be a re-visit, much of what I am going to say here shall be a repetition of what I have already shared in my earlier writings and lectures. Therefore, it shall be a form of reminding oneself, and hopefully my intended audience, once again of what, how and wherefores of some crucial issues that the people of Manipur confront today.

MANIPURI IDENTITY: CRISIS OF A NAME AND ITS TRAJECTORY

Let me begin this personal journey on the theme of identity politics, and destiny of Manipur from that moment when I came across the problematic part of Manipuri identity as a school boy way back in the late 1970s. Towards the end of that decade, I came under the influence of the discourses of what I remembered then as *Meitei Marup*, or as it is understood now as *Meitei or Sanamahi revivalism*. Under those discourses, "Manipur" and "Manipuri" are problematized as "Hindu" categories which have been superimposed on "Kangleipak" and so on. As a young school boy, I dropped "Singh" from my name with my father's permission that was asked for by the school Head Master for the necessary change. (That's how "Angomcha" comes to be part of my name.) And around the same time, I also came to know from a Kabui boy of my age from my locality that for some, the term "Manipuri" only means "Meiteis". I came to know this later aspect much more clearly during my college days in Pune in the 1980s as I discovered that many "tribal" students refused to be members of our student organization because of the term "Manipuri" in our association's name (Poona Manipuri Students Association, PMSA). I took the initiative as the Joint Secretary of the Association to change the name and, rightly or wrongly, we did change the same into "Manipur Students' Association, Poona" (MSAP) on a similar line as adopted by the students in Delhi whose association is called Manipur Students Association, Delhi (MSAD). I must acknowledge that following the change, there was, as far as I recollect, only a marginal increase in the membership from those communities in our association. While name is a crucial aspect of identity, there are obviously other issues as well. Over the years, efforts to find and grapple with those "others issues" have become a crucial part of my professional, and to some sense political engagements.

To get back to the problematic aspects of the name "Manipur Manipuri", my initial position was a rejection of the expression "Manipur" ("*Kangleipak amasung Kangleicha gee wakhalon shagatpa phe*", an article I wrote for a popular monthly called *Lanmei Thanbi* represents that moment)³. As far as I could recollect.

that article was based on a cultural premise rather than religion. Later on, I have addressed the issue by acknowledging its modern geo-political import. An expression of that approach on the issue was laid out in a public Memorial Lecture that I gave in Imphal on 10 June, 2006. Let me share relevant portions of that lecture:

"Manipur has been going through an identity crisis⁴..."Manipuri" is a contested word with divergent meanings. The contestation could be framed by noting the two broad senses in which this word Manipuri has been usually deployed: One, a geo-political sense and the other, the cultural-linguistic sense. In its geo-political sense, Manipuri refers to something that is to do with Manipur as a geo-political entity; in this sense, it also refers to those native inhabitants of the State. But in its cultural-linguistic sense, the meaning of Manipuri has a strong association with those people whose mother tongue is the language called Manipuri, particularly the one spoken by the Meitei, the "ethnic" group that constitutes the majority of the state's population, and by the *Pangal* as their mother tongue. This cultural-linguistic sense is non-territorial or territorially not confined to the State of Manipur in so far as it includes all those people who speak the language as their mother tongue (in places like Assam, Tripura, Burma, Bangladesh etc).

The major crisis of Manipuri identity comes from a lack of fit or disjuncture between these two senses of the word. Taken in terms of the cultural-linguistic sense, Manipuri thus excludes many communities, who are otherwise included under the geo-political sense of the word. Of course, there is a connotation of Manipuri as the lingua franca of the State of Manipur that seeks to incorporate all those native inhabitants of the State. This claim of being the lingua franca is arguably true as the language serves as a medium of communication amongst different communities who speak different languages and dialects in the State. In this sense, this linguistic usage seems to make the two meanings (cultural-linguistic and geo-political) Coterminous. However, this usage as a derivative one, it grows out of or is informed by the geo-political sense of the word. And, therefore, it does not necessarily create a fit between the two meanings (cultural- linguistic and geo-political) of the word "Manipuri". In fact, this

derivative usage, while seemingly makes the cultural-linguistic and geo-political meanings coterminous, paradoxically serves to register the lack of fit between the two. As shown by the controversy around the Manipuri as an "official language", it has been a site where some of the ugly contestations on Manipuri identity have taken place. Just to remind ourselves, we are all familiar with the responses from section of our population, particularly from the hills, during the agitation for the inclusion of Manipuri as a "national language" under the VIII Schedule of the Constitution, or in matters related to the introduction of the language in the curricula of the schools in Manipur etc.⁵

With this lack of fit as a backdrop, the site of this identity crisis has been articulated in terms of "inter-community" or "inter-ethnic" relations. Consequently, the resolutions to the "crisis" have also been sought in terms of those relations.⁶ However, such approach often tends to miss a critical aspect that is at the core of the crisis of *Manipuri* identity: a propensity to define Manipuri identity in terms of linguistic and cultural connotations associated with the community that comes under the nomenclature of the *Meiteis*.

It is worth reminding that historically speaking, the Meiteis was not a name for all those who come under this nomenclature today Initially, it was a name which was only applied to the *Ningthoujas* In the course of time, the name has become a common nomenclature for other cognate communities that are known today as the "seven clans" of the *Meiteis*. In fact, *Meitei* is a generic term for people that also include categories of people who do not come under these "seven clans"⁷ and its inclusionary dimension even incorporates the Bamons and others"⁸. The often heard expressions like *Meitei Bamon* and *Meiter Pangal's* are cases in point.

I suspect that the propensity to define Manipuri in terms of the generic name called the Meiteis has a strong association with a linguistically rooted understanding of human groupings. At one level. such understanding with its philosophical and political inflection could be traced to Europe of 18th and 19th centuries (e.g.. German Romanticism and its ideas such as *nation* as a *volk* which speaks a common language). With the colonial expansion of the European

imperial power, such understanding and notions had also travelled to their colonies. Indeed, it seems more likely than not that the tendency amongst the colonial officials and authors to use the name Manipuri for the people in the valley were informed by such linguistic-cultural understanding of peoplehood. This possibility is indicated in the manner they described their encounters with the denizens of the contemporary region called India's North East. With reference to Manipur, these colonial Europeans described their encounter in terms of a "comparative civilization" with marked structures of power/ administration surrounded by "primitive" and "barbarians" is a case in point.

This exogenous frame of reference¹⁰ have not only constructed different representations of the place and its people, but also resulted in the reification of these exogenous categories through concrete administrative structures (such as the separation of the administration between the valley and hills). Such ideas and practices have brought about critical changes in the ways the "indigenous" people understand their world and conduct themselves as well as the patterns of relationship amongst them. These changes involved a loss of self insofar as these developments rupture the worldviews and organic structures of indigenous life in this part of the globe. Incidentally, these processes sparked off by the colonial intervention were further strengthened by their postcolonial re-productions as well (e.g., people with "comparative civilization" have become "general" and its "barbarians" have become "scheduled tribes" with a juridico-political act in 1951). Thus, the predicaments associated with identity politics in Manipur today are not free from the internalization and appropriation of these exogenous and top down ideas and practices.

And partly shaped by such European ideas and a historically understandable response to the domination of exogenous (particularly, Bengali) literature and culture, a cultural-linguistic awakening took shaped amongst the "educated" (under "modern" education) elites at the beginning of 20th century Manipur. This awakening took the form of a "literary revival" of the language spoken by the Meiteis. The publication of the literary journal *Meitei Chanu* in 1922, which carried a poem (also called *Meitei Chanu*) by poet/novelist Dr. Lamabam

Kamal, was one of the crucial markers of that awakening. It was over this awakening that a socio-political foundation took shape in 1930 the form of Nikhil Hindu Manipuri Mahasabha (established in 1934), and its activities. Indeed, the identity which was registered in the cultural domain in the first two decades of 20th century gradually intruded and expanded into the socio-political sphere in 1930s and 1940.¹¹

The identification of the name *Manipuri* with the identity of a people shaped by the linguistic-cultural inflections of the above trajectory, which is also referred to as the "mainstream"¹², is at the root of the crisis of the *Manipuri* identity. For such identification breeds exclusionary tendency and a corresponding sense of being excluded amongst certain section of the citizenry in Manipur. In a crucial sense, this identification strengthens not only the hold of the cultural-linguistic over the name Manipuri but it also poses a critical challenge to, if not hamper the development of, the geo-political character of *Manipuri* identity.

However, it must be recognized that the churning in the 1930s and 1940s also had traces of a process that sought to break away from such a hold of the cultural-linguistic sense over Manipuri identity. A couple of crucial historical moments, such as the one represented by the 4th session of the Nikhil Hindu Manipuri Mahasabha in 1938¹³ revealed these traces. Indicating a break from the complete identification of the Manipuri identity with the Meiteis, the Mahasabha dropped the word "Hindu" from the name of the organization in a resolution adopted in that session of 1938¹³. In line with this consciousness, the session also put up a demand before the British authority and that of the Manipur to immediately release the then incarcerated Rani Gaidinliu by terming her a "political prisoner Furthermore, insisting that "Manipur State comprises Hills and Valleys...and Hill-men and we, the Meiteis have never been separated and cannot be separated", the session also called for an end to the dual administration, i.e., the administrative separation between the valley and hills of Manipur, which was imposed by the British in 1911.¹⁴

The political character of the above resolutions was further strengthened by the fact that in the then state which was ruled by

the Maharajah and his Durbar, the same session of the Mahasabha also called for the "establishment of a Legislative Council for the attainment of the representative form of Government" in Manipur. This call became more widespread and rigorous in the following years. For instance, a joint meeting of various organizations and political parties from the valley and hills, which was held on 30 November, 1947 at M.D.U. (Manipur Dramatic Union) Imphal, had not only repeated the same demand but also constituted a United Front with Hijam Irabot Singh (Manipur Praja Sangha) and M.K Shimray (Tangkhul Long) as Chairman and Secretary of its Organizing Committee to pursue the demand.

Pressured by the people's movement for "representative form of government", the Maharajah relented to the demand. Thus, the Manipur Constitution Act was introduced (1947) and elections based on universal adult franchise were held (1948) in the valley and hills of Manipur under that constitution. And with those elected members, Manipur Legislative Assembly was inaugurated on 18th October, 1948, and a Council of Ministers took over the administration of the state with the Maharajah as the Constitutional Monarch.

These developments not only underscore the geo-political character of Manipuri identity but also infused that identity with a critical political character which contemporary political theorists called "civic nationalism". It signals a movement from a sense of collectivity based on people's status as subjects of a absolute monarch to that of a collectivity based on right bearing citizens. The self-initiated movement towards a political character of the Manipuri identity was abruptly subverted by a crucial historical event in the life of the people: The "take over" of the administration of Manipur by the Dominion Govt. of India on 15th October, 1949 as per the controversial "Merger Agreement" of 21" September, 1949.¹⁵

MERGER: RUPTURES AND CONTINUITIES

Just as people were beginning to sense the achievement of their collective efforts driven by their democratic aspirations, they suddenly found themselves being "ruled" by a Chief Commissioner with no accountability to them. Ironically, the time when the rest of

the people in India were celebrating their freedom from the alien rule with no accountability to them, and getting ready for the taste of self-rule under democratic ethos, October of 1949 saw the subversion of democratic ethos and a beginning of a bureaucratic rule with no accountability to the people of Manipur.

As the Maharajahs and their officials who were hardly accountable to the people were substituted by a series of Chief Commissioners and Lt Governors for about two decades, and subsequent rule by "summons" and "telephone calls" from New Delhi that continues till date, postcolonial Manipur fails to transform itself. Consequently, its political culture and social ethos of the autocratic and feudal order under the Paramount power of the imperial and colonial British have gone through a politico-cultural mutation after the end of formal colonialism. And that mutation is being fed by the patron-client relationship that marked the political and economic relations between New Delhi and Imphal over the years. A dependent syndrome amongst the people of the state and a weakened sense of self-respect and capacity for self-agency, those characteristics of the people and their political culture that I have shared in the preceding paragraphs are not unrelated to these ruptures and continuities of the postcolonial life in Manipur.

These postcolonial developments are critically linked to the schism and (violent) conflict amongst different communities in the state today. For instance, with the absence of a real centre (or agency) of its own, the state find it increasingly difficult to hold itself. And under the donor driven economy, the economic aspirations and activities of the people have hardly anything to do with the productivity of their labour and ingenuity or the local material resources. Corruption, nepotism and scrambling for one's own shares of the donation from New Delhi, and effort to get one's shares of the spoil by any means (e.g., pronouncing any rhetoric that one fancy to justify their acts or intimidation and murder of those who come in one's way) have become the characteristics of Manipur's political economy. In such a situation, to take cues from Paul Brass¹⁶, manipulating cultural symbols by the competing elites to mobilize

masses to serve their respective interests (e.g., to maximize their shares of the (donated) "scarce resources" from New Delhi) can, if not already, become crucial factors behind the ensuing (inter-group) conflicts. Indeed, (re)inventing identities to demand juridico-political institutions with economic stakes and crafting conflicts amongst people who exist as co-inhabitants or neighbours to further their cause will make sense to such elites. For, that would increase their chances of having a direct access to the corridors of the powerful donor at New Delhi. In short, like many other conflicts in the world, such economic factors can become crucial motives that operate in the inter-group conflicts in the state.

Failure or a cynical refusal to do objective analyses of the political economy and class structures/relations in the state, and communalizing the discourses on under-development and deprivation points can only foster a perpetuation of those structures and ethos that have nurtured the under-development and deprivation. That in a tina state driven economy, the political class, bureaucrats and their hanger-ons are the ones who have access to the wealth and resources of the state, and that over the years such new classes evolved from different communities have been exploiting their access to the power and economic resources of the state to further their personal well-being, often by swindling public money, have been completely denied by the communalized articulations on under-development.

Incidentally, a statement issued by the Angami Public Organization (APO) on December 20, 1997 during its Silver Jubilee Celebration. states, among other, "What we call "Naga Economy" is mainly cash transferred from Delhi to Kohima. And what we call "Naga politics" is now largely a ruthless scramble by all of us, "overground" and "underground", to lay our hands on the cash for which we have not sweated"¹⁷. That the "Naga Integrationists" and their likes in Manipur chose to suspend such a rational analysis when it comes to Manipur speaks volumes of the motivated nature of the communalized arguments on under-development and deprivation. Thus, to say the least, such an approach only ensures the continued enslavement and deprivation of the common people by shielding those who thrive on such enslavement and deprivation of the masses.

Such misleading campaign is not confined to the economic issues only. As a part of the identity politics, it is also reflected in the way the idea of history has been deployed, by both those who seek to tear apart Manipur and those who speak for the defence of "territorial integrity" of the state.

TWO TALES: HISTORY AS A SITE OF CONFLICT

I believe, like many postcolonial scholars do, that the idea of history is a crucial site of conflicts which are born out of identity politics¹⁸, including in Manipur. For instance, the "Naga integrationists" have been invoking the "Unique history" of the Nagas in an effort to tear apart Manipur. On the other hand, the defenders of Manipur's territorial integrity have also been invoking what they called 2000 years old history of Manipur. Let me turn to the problematic aspects of these two deployments of history in the ensuing "Manipuri-Naga" confrontations that seems to have substituted the decades old "Indo-Naga" conflict.

First, the invocation of the "Unique History" of the Nagas in relation to certain section of the population in the Manipur hills has its own shares of problems.

First, the constitutional reform (Govt. of India Act, 1935) that followed the Simon Commission dealt with what was then referred to as the "problem of two Indias": British India and "Princely States. The Memorandum of the Naga Club to the Simon Commission (1929) primarily dealt with the Naga Hills of the then British Indian Provin of Assam, and therefore it had no bearing on Manipur as a "Princely State". In fact, the expression "excluded" or "partially excluded" the Govt. of India Act (1935) referred to those areas that had nothing to do with the areas or people or polity of Manipur as a "Princely State". Indeed, the same provision that carried these two (excluded" and "partially excluded) tried these two to be "administered" by "the Governor of Assam" "at his discretion."

Interestingly, the status of being "excluded" or "partial excluded" of these areas and the office/power to of India Act many Nagas read the same provision as a proof of their being outs of the (constitutional arrangement of the then) British India!

Tragically, having misread, and even ironically celebrated, this colonial arrangement of removing from the normal constitutional parameters while still being administered through (sovereign) "discretion", many Human Rights activists in Nagaland or Manipur will hardly recognize that the notorious AFSPA is the post-colonial return of the same spirit/arrangement of exceptionalism!

Second, the areas or people or polity of Manipur as a "Princely State" had nothing to do with the Nine Points Agreement (1947), signed between the Naga National Council and the then Governor of Assam, which pertained to the then Naga Hills and Tuensang Area as a District. Third, the Naga Plebiscite (1951) conducted by the Naga National Council was not held in Manipur, and therefore, it did not represent the will and wishes of the people in the state.

Fourth, the total boycott of the first and the second General Elections to the Indian Parliament by the Nagas had no bearing on the history of Manipur. For, like their valley counterparts, the people in the Hills of Manipur had not only participated in those elections but also sent R. Keishing (1952) and R. Suisa (1957) as MPs from Manipur. Indeed, to insist that the Nagas had totally boycotted those elections would only mean that those who took part in the same elections and these two gentlemen from the Tangkhul community were not Nagas!

Therefore, invoking the "Unique History" of the Nagas as a rationale to vivisect Manipur on "ethnic" cum religious lines is to work against the sanctity of the historical truth of Nagas' "Unique History" or that of Manipur.

Besides this invocation of history, contemporary Naga nationalism also has another aspect that has become a cause for concern: its tendency of constantly invoking the Meitei as the "other", often couched in war-like rhetoric with expressions such as "enemy", "befitting response" or "hit back" etc.

At one level, this is an understandable posture. After all, over and above the pressing need to overcome the "inter-tribal" rivalry, the Naga nationalists are in Peace Talks with GOI, Nagas' traditional adversary in their nationalist struggle. And GOI has reportedly ruled

out Nagas" "sovereignty", the prime mover of Naga nationalism. In such a scenario, positioning the Meiteis as "the" adversary (in the place of the GOI) can become handy to enhance "Naga integration as a motivational substitute for "sovereignty" to sustain the movement while simultaneously strengthening the in-group solidarity among different Naga "tribes" vis-à-vis an "outside enemy".

However, it must be reiterated that nationalist articulation rests on a clear distinction between "friend" and "enemy" with hatred for that proclaimed "enemy" can only produce or promise, as history tells us, genocidal purging of the "other" from a given area and polity. And ultimately such nationalism is self-destructive. One fervently hopes that the Nagas do not succumb to the temptation of making their liberating nationalism into a conservative ideology.

Finally, all state boundaries and cartographical representations in the world are "artificial" insofar as these are historical products of human actions. And modern (nationalist) identities are historically situated realities. Beyond the propaganda, "Nagalim" and the Naga national identity cannot be exceptions to these historical truths.

Problematic deployment of "history" is not the sole prerogative of the Naga nationalists; many defenders of Manipur's "territorial integrity" also commit similar, if not identical, mistakes. As stated earlier, the insinuation that Manipur has existed as a "nation-state for 2000 years, leave alone from "time immemorial", is a classic example. With an internalization of alien categories and perspective, many Meiteis tend to take a pride in their own written history and correspondingly mock at the Nagas for their lack of the same. Such articulations not only deny the problematic aspects of their narrative but also reaffirm their inability to free themselves from the alien ideas and perspectives. Let us turn briefly to some of these issues.

One of the most popular articulations that have caught the imagination of the people is that Manipur is a "nation-state" with 2000 years old "history". And this history of Manipur as a "nation state" usually begins, following the records of the Royal Chronicles such as the Cheitharol Kumpapa, with the story of the Meidingu Pakhangba in 33 A.D. The expansion and reign of this dynasty forms the main, if not the axis, of this popular history of Manipur as a "nation-state"...¹⁹

"This articulation of self is problematic in many ways. Let me mention two crucial aspects of the problem. First, the above history is undoubtedly a product of a "state-centric" historiography, and if some historians are to be believed, "state-centric" historiography often takes the form of majoritarian articulation. This view is not an unwarranted position. A history that forms its axis around the expansion of political authority of the Ningthouja dynasty, with the concomitant stories of defeats and subjugations of various peoples along the way, understandably becomes the history of the Meiteis. And to articulate a collective self through such history obviously excludes others (other than those under the rubric of Meitei), on the one hand and, ironically, on the other, makes subjugated selves out of fellow citizen in the present. Thus, if some people say that "they have never been a part of Manipur", I am afraid, their claim must have something to do with the above popular history that articulates the identity of Manipur. And if such historiography is inevitable, the conflict and estrangement that marked the present-day Manipur is also inevitable. Perhaps, then, we need to rethink such historiography and any notions of its "inevitability".

Second, such history seeks legitimacy for an anachronistically imagined Manipur, which is temporally and spatially frozen throughout the 2000 years of its history. The idea of Manipur as a "nation" with "firm boundary" since "time immemorial" is an example of such narrative. While this is an understandable need or even an imperative of a "nationalist" imagination, it is nonetheless problematic. It restrains us from doing an objective rendering of the evolution of the structure of the political authority or the spatiality of "state" or the shades and spectrum of the people's consciousness in the making of Manipur as we know today. In the process, how different peoples from different spatial locations with different "cultural" practices have interacted, intermingled under different regimes of power or political authorities in the evolution of the present state, are left outside our purview. As a result, the partaking of different peoples across times and spaces in the making of present-day Manipur, arguably an important element of a narrative to produce a sense of belonging or wholesome and holistic self, have been subsequently subverted.²⁰

Different forms of consciousness of collectivities and relationships have presumably accompanied the transformation of spaces dotted by small human settlements, villages and principalities into a kingdom, then to a monarchic state and a modern state. The consciousness and cosmologies of the people under the social order of kinship groups, insulated (and often fortified) villages under the chiefs and the suzerainty of a sovereign monarch, are bound to be different from that of the secularized political order inhabited by the enfranchised people in a modern state. Manipur as an entity marked by a hierarchy of loyalty with the King at the top with his officials, the village chiefs and *sagei aahals* (family patriarchs) below, is not the same Manipur under a democratic and republican order inhabited by equal, at least in principle, individual citizens. A history that produces, sustains and legitimizes an anachronistically imagined Manipur is against such an understanding.

I believe that the popular historical narrative renders the Meiteis a la "national mainstream", and reduces the different trajectories and life-forms of the people to a monochromatic narrative of that "mainstream". It has a propensity to propagate implicitly, if not explicitly, the idea that all other communities are mere peripheral appendices to the "mainstream" Meitei. It even nurtures an assumption that the Meiteis constitute the necessary as well as sufficient condition that underlies the geo-political reality of Manipur. In such a worldview, "integration" often represents a wish to have a homogenous entity, which comes in direct contradiction with the realities of the heterogeneity of life. The alienation and fragmentation of identities in Manipur today is a direct manifestation of that contradiction. In short, the popular history neither captures the historicity of the complexities of the evolution of Manipur as a geo political reality nor does it enable the reality to sustain itself.

I believe that such rendering of history is as mythical as the refusal to acknowledge the historicity of the reality called Manipur as a geo political entity amongst certain sections of our society. In fact, in a way, both could be taken as the two sides of the same coin or, perhaps like the interlocking quantum particles of Physics. I might as venture to suggest that a change in position of one might bring about a reciprocal change in the other. Of course, this suggestion is a

statement of "probability", based on an assumption, as in quantum state, which is reportedly pretty "unpredictable" as suggested by the Heisenberg's "uncertainty principle", that human affairs cannot be accurately predicted.

If such a history is problematic, what is the alternative? The answer is perhaps producing alternative histories, to use the expression popular amongst the subaltern historians. These alternative histories could be in the form of social histories, "histories from below", histories of the marginal communities, women etc. One can also think of histories that critically engage with the nationalist and state-centric narratives. Though not a professional historian, I am aware that these are not only popular amongst, but also fairly representative of, much of the works of many contemporary historians. However, to get a flavour of the implications of writing such alternative histories for us in Manipur, allow me to share an example. Let us think of writing a history on the evolution or nature of YU Shungba (brewing of local liquor) in Manipur. In terms of its production and consumption, and cultural meanings and economy, one is likely to come across shared spaces as well as markers of specific enclaves amongst different communities. I believe that the identities we might see through such history would be different from the history that produces identities of the modern "nation-state". While the former is likely to reveal "fuzzy" identities, that is, those which are codified and performed differently in temporally specific spaces for specific purposes, the latter is likely to register and justify reified, bounded and enumerated identities. A work of this kind shall not be a rare specimen, as I have indicated, amongst the contemporary historians.

DO WE GET THE DATE AND THE MONTH RIGHT?

If politics is all about acumen and timing, the Chief Minister and his advisors had got it all wrong when he announced 18 June as a holiday in 2005. If he actually thought that we needed a day to energize the people to work beyond the narrow interests based on religion, place of birth/residence, sex, language, he should have declared 18th October as the "Integrity Day". After all, "Integrity Day should be about coming together of people, of common hope

and aspiration, and of moving beyond the cocoon of myopic visions. and of commemorating a historically significant day that secures Manipur a place of pride in the entire South Asia. It should not be day to remind the schism and division of fractured identity of Manipur

If evoking "2000 years of history" as a "nation" to counter the threat to the integrity of Manipur actually obfuscates the political and socio-economic realities of Manipur, commemorating "Integrity Day on two different dates (18th June and 4th August) not only strengthens that obfuscation but deepens the fault lines of an obviously divided "people" of Manipur. There is no point in shying away from the fact that 18th June 2001, or 4th August 1997, was for protecting the integrity of the state. But these events also spoke of the divided nature of the "people" of Manipur. If it were not so, rallies for the integrity of Manipur should have also been seen in Tamenglong or Chandel, if not Ukhrul and Senapati. Honesty and courage demand us to confront, not deny or obfuscate the divided character of our selfhood. And sincerity also demands that when we say the "people of Manipur", it cannot only be the "people" of a particular habitat or members and supporters of a particular organization who commemorates a particular day, it has to be the "people" of Manipur expressing their wish to be together and seeking their moral right to exist as a people and individuals with dignity. Tragic as it can get, as we seek to commemorate these dates, 18th June or 4th August, we shall also be paradoxically reminding ourselves of not only the zeal and sacrifices to protect Manipur but also the divergence and schism of the very idea of "people of Manipur". Indeed, in 2005, by declaring 18th June as a holiday to commemorate it as the "Integrity Day", the Chief Minister has only managed to bring out the division much more sharply. While some positively received his decision, others responded by imposing economic blockade on the national highways (39 & 53)

There is enough reason to choose 18th October as "People's Solidarity Day" of Manipur. It was on this date in 1948 the then Maharajah of Manipur inaugurated the first ever legislative assembly in the entire South Asia which was constituted through a democratic election based on the principle of universal adult franchise. It was the day when the representatives of the people of Manipur, irrespective of

language, religion, sex or place of residence etc, came together to mark their transformation from being mere subjects of a sovereign to that of becoming democratic citizens who shared the sovereign power with the king. It was truly an epoch making historical moment of imagining a new collectivity, of peoplehood in modern-terms. The Chief Minister would have rekindled a hope by reminding the pride with which the Maharajah of Manipur declared on that day, that "just as the Sun rises earlier in the east, (Manipur has) taken the lead in the direction of democratic government, based on adult franchise and joint electorate"²¹. Moreover, the Chief Minister should also have realized that the struggle for statehood in the 1960s and 1970s was not only inspired by the legacy of that Assembly of 1948 (during the struggle, it was often expressed in terms of the "restoration" of the democratic and responsible government in Manipur) but had also brought the people and their leaders from both the valley and hills together in Manipur. Indeed, 18th October is day of coming together of f people, of hope and aspiration, and beyond the cocoon of myopic visions, it is a historically significant day that secures Manipur a place of pride in the entire South Asia.

By declaring 18th October as the "Integrity Day", we will assert the supremacy of the people and their representatives and a legacy of a historical lineage of an epoch making development in 1948. It will set off a recovery of the aspects of our lost sense of selfhood, a political ethos wherein every community have taken part in shaping the destiny of the people in the state.

End Note: Understanding the Challenges

Along with such issues, we must understand that the real issue that the politics of "Naga Integration", as it stands today, poses to Manipur is not to its territorial integrity per se. But what it does critically challenge is the very character of Manipur's historically evolved polity that marks it as a geo-political and cultural entity. It is fundamentally a problem of or a threat to the very idea of "we, the people" (of Manipur) which forms the legitimate basis of modern Polity across the globe. Therefore, the issue of territory is at best a Consequential or symptomatic concern, and at worst, a dubious smoke- screen that hides the real issue.

The challenge before Manipur is primarily a matter of political imagination and ways to sustain the same. It is neither some dispute over land nor about people's 'emotions' about each other, this unfortunately, is something that many seemed to have missed. And on a similar plane, those who look at "Naga integration" as merely harmless expression of a positive desire of a group of people wanting to live together as one under the same 'administrative unit completely or conveniently misses the dangerous political face of the same desire as it is expressed in relation to Manipur.

That face, the 'other side' of the politics of "Naga integration" is the belief that different 'ethnic', religious, linguistic or cultural groups have different socio-economic and political interests and therefore they do not and cannot have a common destiny as a people under the same polity. If it is not for this belief, what is the rationale that justifies the effort to tear apart the socio-economic and political fabric of the inter-dependent communities who inhabit, and partake in the socio-economic and political life of, Manipur as a geo-political entity for years, even before the advent of Naga nationalist movement or the post-colonial Indian State towards the middle of the last century?

The idea that mono-cultural/ethnic/linguistic/religious entity must necessarily constitute a political entity is an outdated 19th century European myth propagated by its brand of nationalism. Besides, this myth is counter-intuitive to the heterogeneity of human existence and the fact that no country in this world is culturally homogeneous. But more importantly, to insist that one belongs to an 'ethnic group', which is also largely coterminous with a particular faith (Christianity), and therefore he or she (and the group) does not and cannot have a shared socio-economic and political interests and destiny with other groups in a society of inter-dependent communities is a classic expression of what is called in South Asia, 'communalism'.

And history has told us of the consequences of communal politics associated with the Partition of Indian subcontinent. Given this, can the people of Manipur, for that matter, the North East, afford a similar history to be repeated amidst them? And for a region which has already been gifted with an ethnic conundrum, not un-related to the process of 'ethnically' driven 'Balkanization' of the region started in the 1960s, do we need to further deepen the same process of

fragmentation and tensions amongst the cognate communities who inhabit this troubled part of the globe?

On the other hand, despite their historical experience or professed positions on communalism, will the people of India and the Government at New Delhi support, if not nurture, communal politics in its North East as a strategic measure to divide the people all in the name of 'national interest to establish the hold of the Indian State over what it considers to be a "strategic region" vis-à-vis China inhabited by people who are suspected of their 'loyalty to India' (by some of the founding fathers of the Indian nation-state and their true inheritors)?

These are critical questions that the people in Manipur and the North East must address. And this can be done only when one is able to see that the fundamental issue that one confronts in Manipur is not merely, if at all the basic issue is of, the territorial integrity of the state but the fate of a polity that have far reaching implications for the people in not only Manipur but also the entire region called the North East.

However, it must also be acknowledged that 'communalism in South Asia has been a by-product of an un-reflexive, self-righteous and sectarian (nationalist) politics of majoritarianism. Therefore, one must also be equally on guard against such self-righteous sectarian tendencies amidst us. Indeed, there are remnants of regressive elements in our society which also incidentally help the cause of those who seek to tear apart Manipur. One must out rightly reject any idea that smacks of imperial nostalgia which seeks to appropriate Manipur. Indeed, mindlessly harping on the exploits of the kings and queens, particularly their autocratic and feudal ethos, is against the present and future of our collectivity. Similarly, one must counter any form of majoritarianism that subverts a genuine democratic ethos from taking its roots in our society. Besides, the high-brow and self-righteous attitude and the repugnant superiority complex of the obsolete chauvinists that heap humiliation on fellow citizens must be eliminated. In any case, irrespective of the challenges posed by the "Naga integrationists", lighting such regressive elements is critical to shape a better future for all of us in Manipur.

And it must go without saying that knee-jerk and episode reactions based on militaristic ethos and political myopia can never produce a way out of the hurdles posed by the disguised and systematic campaign against Manipur's politics of inter-dependence and co-existence of people belonging to different 'ethnic', religious, linguistic and cultural groups. Neither such responses are the right ways to address the pressing problems and genuine grievances and aspiration, however one may agree with those or not, of one's fellow citizen. In fact, such knee-jerk and episodic responses will only add fuel to the deafening communal harangue and war cries, which synchronized seamlessly with the contradictory rhetoric of peace and good neighborly love, and the smug politics that have repeatedly blackmailed the people and strangled ordinary people and daily wage-earners in the state through blockades over the years.

It is high time that the Government, political class, civil society groups, intellectuals and those who believe in the idea of Manipur and its 'multicultural ethos' sit together and work towards defeating the communal virus that afflicts the body-politics and ensure an honourable and lasting solution to our pressing problems to bring dignity, honour, peace and prosperity to the beleaguered people of Manipur. The 19th century European myth of the "nation-state" had sought to sell an idyllic image of a mono-cultural political formation. That image had given two World Wars, and mimicking that in South Asia had resulted in colossal violence and uprooting of people from their ancestral homes, and wars and mistrust to haunt the people even today. We must learn from history and evolve alternative ways to understand our world and re-fashion our politics for a common destiny.²²

NOTES & REFERENCES

- ¹ For a reflection on this in intellectual life, see Manipuri Intellectual Style, <http://kanglaonline.com/columnist/manipuri-intellectual-style/>; and also for similar implication on the issue of leadership. Extraordinary Challenges of Extraordinary Times <http://kanglaonline.com/2012/10/extraordinary-challenges-of-extraordinary-times/>
- ² See, Manipuri Intellectual Style, Op. cit.
- ³ I do not have a copy of the article and unfortunately I also do not exactly recollect the year. But as far as my memory goes, it was the August issue of the monthly in the year 1983 or 1984 or 1985.
- ⁴ For a comparative reflection on the issue, see the discussion on Manipuri identity by the well known historian Gangmumei Kamei ("Crisis of Identity in Manipur", Expression of the Freedom. Imphal: The Freedom, 1994) and anthropologist M.C Arunkumar ("The Three question: Test of Conformity A study on Meitei Political Culture". Anthropologist. 7. 2, 2005).
- ⁵ See, Akoijam, A. Bimol (2006) Towards a wholesome holistic self: On silence, identity and coloniality of the postcolonial, Imphal: ASMT (First Arambam Somorendra Memorial Lecture)
- ⁶ See, Akoijam, ibid
- ⁷ There are sageis (clans or families) which constitute the Meiteis that do not belong to any of the "seven clans"
- ⁸ However, in the sense of an in-between group comparison reflected in social practices (e.g., marriage), Bamons, "Meiteis", and Pangals would still be taken as different categories of people.
- ⁹Such usages reveal the linguistic-cultural underpinning of the name Meiteis.
- ¹⁰ See, Akoijam, A. Bimol, 2001, How history repeats itself. Economic and Political Weekly, Vol 36, No. 30, pp. 2807-2812.
- ¹¹ The evolution of modern identity (of the nationalist kind) from the cultural to the political awakening, initially led by elites whose hegemonic dominance represented by the appropriation of their ideas and interests by the members of the other classes is a well known phenomenon (see, Hobsbawm, E.J., 1990, Nations and nationalism since 1780, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. and also Chatterjee, Partha, 1994, The nation and its fragments Colonial and postcolonial histories, Delhi: OUP: Aloysius, G. 1997, Nationalism without nation in India, New Delhi: OUP)
- ¹² For a version of this idea of "the mainstream", see, Singh, N. Tombi (1975) Manipur, the mainstream, Imphal: Chitrebirentombichand Khorjeirup
- ¹³It is important to note even otherwise that the name Manipuri is not an exclusive name for the (Hindu) Meiteis is indicated by the fact the word Manipuri was qualified by the word Hindu.
- ¹⁴ For a re-production of the copy of the resolutions containing the demands adopted in that session of the Nikhil Hindu Manipuri Mahasabha in 1938, See Singh, Karam Manimohan (1989), Hijam Irabot Singh and Political Movements in Manipur, Delhi: B.R Publishing Corporation (pp. 75-77)
- ¹⁵ The manner in which this agreement was signed between the representatives of the Govt. of India and the Maharajah of Manipur remained an unsavoury moment that continues to haunt the Indian state and people of the state till date (see, Singh, Lt. Col. H. Bhuban, 1988, The merger of Manipur, Imphal: Pritam Haobam; Singh, Mayengbam Brajamohan, 2004, Shillong 1949, Imphal: Mayengbam Akshayakumar Singh, Annexation of Manipur, 1949. a publication produced by Peoples' Democratic Movement, 1995. Imphal)
- ¹⁶ See, Brass R. Paul, 1991, Ethnicity and nationalism: Theory and comparison, New Delhi: Sage.
- ¹⁷ See, Chasie, Charles, 1999, The Naga Imbroglia (a personal perspective), Kohima: Standard Printers & Publishers
- ¹⁸ See, Nandy, Ashis, 1995, History's forgotten doubles. History and Theory: 34:2, pp.44-66.
- ¹⁹ See. First Arambam Somerendro Memorial Lecture "Towards a wholesome holistic self: On silence, identity and coloniality of the postcolonial", Imphal: ASMT, 2006
- ²⁰ Ibid.
- ²¹ Sanajaoba, Naorem, 1993, Manipur: Treatise and documents (1110- 1977), New Delhi: Mittal Publications (pp.434).
- ²² See, Beyond Propaganda and Imperial Nostalgia, http://e-pao.net/epSubPageExtractor.asp?src=news_section.Muivah_Visit_201005.Muivah_Articles_201006.Beyond_propaganda_and_imperial_nostalgia" also Manipur and Naga Politics: Dangers of Sectarian Ethno-nationalist Politics, <http://>

